

MIRNA can be a part of both the onset and cure of Coronary heart disease

Motaz Dowaidar^{1,2}

¹Department of Bioengineering, King Fahd University of Petroleum
and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran 31261, Saudi Arabia.

²Interdisciplinary Research Center for Hydrogen and Energy Storage
(IRC-HES), King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals
(KFUPM), Dhahran, 31261, Saudi Arabia.

Abstract- Cardiovascular disease causes the worst destruction. The study suggests that miRNAs are involved in the cause, occurrence, and prognosis of CVD. Even though they were discovered in 1993, their functions have not been well understood; more recently, they are known to control gene expression as well as fine-tune many biochemical processes. A myriad of miRNAs contribute to the pathogenesis of coronary diseases. Most experiments on miRNAs have shown that miRNA is either increased or decreased under various pathophysiological conditions, but its function in CVD remains a mystery. Often suggested to be involved in the pathophysiology of CVD, the discovery of disease biomarkers that are useful in the processing would highlight the relevance of miRNAs for diagnostics and therapy development of CVDs. During the early stages, the use of miRNAs as therapies has the potential to impact therapeutics. More refined technologies are also required to develop miRNA as biomarkers and treatments. Indeed, additional regional and/population research is needed to address any possible challenges or issues. The introduction of new gene therapies discoveries is on the way.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular disorders (CVDs) are the leading cause of death in people all around the world. Familial hypercholesterolemia, cardiomyopathies, congenital heart disorders (CHD), thoracic aortic aneurysms, coronary artery disease, and heart failure are also examples of CVDs (1). Despite advances in pharmacological and surgical armamentaria, the prognosis for CVDs is still low (2).

A large body of research suggests that genetic elements and changes in their expression profile are the primary causes of cardiac pathology (3). MicroRNAs (miRNAs) have been one of the most important molecular targets in research on the causes of CVDs and the treatment of their symptoms over the last few decades. In the human genome, there are about 2300 mature miRNA genes (4). Victor Ambros et al found Lin-4 in *Caenorhabditis elegans* for the first time in 1993. The discovery of the Let-7 miRNA by Gary Ruvkun et al in 2001, however, was what really attracted biologists' attention to miRNAs. MiRNAs have been implicated in a wide range of cellular biological processes, including growth, cycle control, proliferation, differentiation, apoptosis, and angiogenesis, as well as immune and cardiovascular responses to pathogens and cancers ((5), (6), (7)).

Translational science aims to draw on fundamental scientific research and develop new diagnosis and therapeutic modalities. Analysis of miRNA function during cardiovascular system growth, for example, may lead to novel miRNA-based therapeutic strategies. To that end, we present an outline of the most recent results on the role of miRNA control in cardiac growth in the current research.

II. MICRORNA BIOGENESIS PATHWAYS AND MECHANISMS OF ACTION

Primary microRNA (pri-miRNA) transcripts are produced in the canonical biogenesis pathway by RNA polymerase II or RNA polymerase III transcription of miRNA genes (8,9). Like messenger RNAs (mRNAs), most pri-miRNA transcripts are polyadenylated at 3' and capped at 5'. Droscha converts pri-miRNAs into precursor microRNAs with the aid of its cofactor DiGeorge syndrome essential region 8 (DGCR8), a double-stranded RNA-binding protein (pre-miRNAs). Exportin 5 (XPO5) exports pre-miRNAs from the nucleus to the cytoplasm with the aid of RAN-GTP (10,11). Dicer-I cleaves pre-miRNAs into mature miRNAs in the cytoplasm (12,13). The consequence of Dicer-mediated dicing is an approximately 22-nucleotide miRNA duplex with two nucleotide overhangs at 3'; however, noncanonical miRNA biogenesis pathways produce identical mature miRNA products that vary in processing steps (5). Dicer-I is assisted in the dicing step by the trans-activating reaction of RNA-binding protein (12,13). The RNA-induced silencing complex (RISC) is then activated by the mature miRNA (14). For miRNAs with Argonaute proteins as the main effector portion, this complex is known as the "miRISC" (6). The guide miRNA strand, which normally has a weak 5' terminus, is chosen to guide the miRISC to the target miRNA, while the other strand, which is degraded during this operation, is referred to as the "passenger strand" or "miRNA star strand" (15,16). The complementary sequence in the target mRNA is searched for by a

RISC filled with miRNA. The degree of complementarity between miRNA:mRNA target sequences determines the outcome of miRNA-mediated gene regulation (5). As a consequence, partial complementarity between miRNA:mRNA target sequences causes translation repression, which is common in animals (17), while complete complementarity causes the target miRNA to be degraded by Argonaute proteins' endonuclease activity (17,18).

III. THE FUNCTION OF MICRORNAS IN THE FORMATION OF THE HEART

The prognosis of CVDs would be improved if the basic molecular dynamics of cardiogenesis signalling pathways were better understood (19). Multiple transcription factors control the expression of cardiac genes, much as they do in other organs (20). MiRNAs are classified as factors that regulate cardiac gene expressions as post-transcriptional regulators (21). In cardiac cells, including cardiomyocytes, fibroblasts, and endothelial cells, a large number of miRNAs are dysregulated (22). The importance of miRNAs in cardiogenesis was first shown in a study in which two distinct exons of the Dicer gene were deleted in murine embryos, resulting in angiogenesis disruption and embryonic death (23,24). Imbalanced miRNA expressions in developing heart progenitor cells can lead to congenital or structural defects, such as poor cell migration, proliferation, and classification into incorrect cell types. Since cardiac cells have reached the end of their differentiation, certain structural defects are not repaired properly (25). In this regard, experiments on miRNA have shown that a single miRNA can play a role in both heart formation and function ((26), (27), (28), (29)). In the zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), research has also shown that miRNAs regulate cardiac production by regulating TBX2, CSPG2, and NOTCH1 (30,31). Overall, these findings highlight the several roles that miRNAs play in cardiac growth.

3.1. MiR-1, miR-130, and miR-133: Their Functions

The miR-1 family members miR-1-1 and miR-1-2, as well as the miR-133 family members miR-133a-1, miR-133a-2, and miR-133b, are all transcribed from the same pre-miRNA transcript (29). MiR-1 and miR-133, which are abundant at the start of cardiac development, can work together to facilitate the division of embryonic stem cells into mesodermal cells. However, as the heart develops, it begins to exhibit certain contradictory characteristics. For example, miR-1 promotes and miR-133 inhibits embryonic stem cell differentiation into cardiomyocytes ((32), (33), (34)), and miR-1 and miR-133 regulate the serum response factor (SRF) transcription factor's operation. SRF regulates cardiac and smooth muscle differentiation genes and is active in cell cycle development (27,35,36). MiR-1 is the first miRNA to be linked to heart growth, accounting for roughly 40% of all heart miRNAs. Furthermore, via its targets, the IRX5 and Hand2 transcription factors, this miRNA controls cardiac activity (23). MiR-1 expression raises cardiomyocyte contribution, thus lowering endothelial cell fate (37). MiR-1 has been identified as a target of the cardiac repolarization regulator IRX5, which promotes myocyte differentiation (26). Qian et al found that the transcription factor NKX2-5 may be considered a direct inhibitor of miR-1 in *Drosophila melanogaster* (38). Another miRNA, known as "MiR-133," inhibits cardiomyocyte proliferation in the developing heart by regulating the proteins cyclinD2 (39), SRF 3, and CDC42, which are essential for cell cycle and proliferation control (40). In this regard, a similar study suggested that injecting miR-133 into *Xenopus* embryos could halt cell proliferation and differentiation (29). Other miRNAs have also been found to play an important role in the development of the heart. For example, by suppressing fibroblast growth factor 8, miR-130 promotes the overexpression of bone morphogenetic protein 2 (BMP2), NKX2-5, and GATA4 (FGF8). FGF8 and BMP2 proteins, which are secreted by the endoderm, may also influence cardiac differentiation (41).

3.2. MiR-128a, miR-138, and miR-218 positions

MiR-128a, which is widely expressed in the brain and skeletal muscles, rises during myoblast differentiation. MiR-128a overexpression inhibits cell proliferation in myoblasts by attacking insulin receptor substrate 1, while miR-128a suppression facilitates cardiomyocyte production (42). MiR-128a can play a role in the early stages of heart development, according to Hoelscher et al, since it affects the differentiation of cardiomyocyte progenitor cells into various subtypes of cardiomyocytes (43). MiR-138, another miRNA involved in heart growth, is found in the zebrafish's cardiac-specific domains. Via its targets *aldh1a2* and *cspg2*, this miRNA is needed for the proper patterning of chamber-specific genes (44). The heart is protected from *tbx5* overexpression-induced deficiencies while miR-218 is suppressed, demonstrating miR-218's function in cardiac growth and structural defects (45). MiR-218 is a critical factor in the development of the heart tube in zebrafish, and it modulates the role of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) signaling in this phase (46).

MYH6 and MYH7 are two important genes with high expression in the heart (47). 3.3. Cardiac myomiR families (miR-208a/miR-499) Recent research has discovered that miRNAs are encoded from within MYH genes such as MYH6 and MYH7, which encode the miR-208 family (miR-208a and miR-208b) and miR-499, respectively, in the developing heart (48). As a result, miR-208a is regarded as a critical stress gene; but, under typical circumstances, miR-208a knockout mice survived with normal heart function (28,49). Furthermore, miR-208a controls the *CX40*, *HOPX*, and *GATA4* genes, which are considered to be important regulators of heart expression profile and function, as well as negatively regulating *THRAP1* (a major member of the thyroid signal pathway) (49.) Via the repression of *SOX6*, MiR-499 enhanced the differentiation of cardiac progenitors into cardiomyocytes (25). *SOX6*, a direct target of miR-499, has been shown to play important roles in cardiomyocyte viability, proliferation inhibition, and apoptosis (50). After an acute myocardial infarction (MI), miR-499, which was previously only known to be expressed in cardiomyocytes, will also be overexpressed (51). Furthermore, miR-499 promotes ventricular specification during the differentiation of cardiac Human Embryonic Stem Cells (hESCs) (52). MiR-499 knock-down mice have a higher rate of apoptosis at the posterior differentiation level, according to several studies.

3.4 The miR-17-92 cluster

In the embryonic and postnatal stages of cardiogenesis, the miR-17-92 cluster, which includes miR-17, miR-18a, miR-19a, miR-20a, and miR-92-1, is essential (53). By targeting ISL1 and TBX1 in progenitor cells, Wang et al discovered that the miR-17-92 cluster could simulate myocardial differentiation (54). The increased expression of the miR-17-92 cluster will promote endothelial cell proliferation, but it also suppresses FOG-2 (55). In mice, dysfunctional miR-17-92 causes pathological cardiomyocyte progenitor cell division into cardiomyocytes (54). MiR-19, as a key cluster member, promotes cardiomyocyte proliferation by directly inhibiting its target, phosphatase and tensin homolog (PTEN). MiR-19, according to Ai et al, will mimic irregular cardiac production in zebrafish progenitor cells (56).

The miR-15 family of microRNAs (miR-15) is a family of microRNAs

MiR-15a, miR-15b, miR-16, miR-195, and miR-497, all members of the miR-15 family, have been shown to inhibit cardiomyocyte proliferation (57). MiR-195, which is upregulated during cardiac development and capable of fostering cell cycle arrest and suppressing mitotic genes (58), is one of these family members. The miR-15 family members are upregulated in the murine heart, according to Porrello et al, and are capable of inhibiting cell-cycle arrest genes. The inhibition of the miR-15 family members induces myocyte proliferation in young murine models in this way (59).

3.6. miR-143 and miR-145's positions

MiR-143 and miR-145 are transcribed as a bicistronic cluster and are highly expressed in the early stages of murine cardiogenesis. As a result, these mesenchymal miRNAs play a key role in vascular smooth muscle cell regulation (34). In response to defects or growth factors, highly plastic vascular smooth muscle cells may modulate their phenotypes between proliferative, migratory, and differentiated states. Furthermore, BMPs and transforming growth factor beta-1 have the ability to upregulate miR-143 and miR-145 expression (60). MiR-145, which is thought to promote vascular smooth muscle cell differentiation, inhibits proliferation of cardiac defects in this way. MiR-143, on the other hand, inhibits Elk1's ability to cause vascular smooth muscle cell proliferation (61).

3.7. MiR-126's Role

The internal surfaces of the vasculature are formed by endothelial cells. MiRNAs, such as miR-126, which is an endothelial-specific miRNA, stimulate vascular growth and angiogenesis. The endothelial cells of miR-126 knockout mice show a lack of angiogenesis and reaction to FGF2 in an in vivo sample (58). In cardiac neovascularization after MIs, these null mice develop leaky vessels, hemorrhage, and partial embryonic lethality (62).

3.8 Let-7

During the formation of the murine heart, many members of the Let-7 family, including Let-7a, Let-7d, Let-7e, and Let-7f, were upregulated. Let-7 is needed and necessary for the differentiation of cardiac embryonic stem cells and the maturation of cardiomyocytes (63,64), as it is the most overexpressed miRNA during human cardiac development.

3.9 Other miRNAs

Other miRNAs that have been shown to play a role in cardiac differentiation include miR-669 and miR-204 (25). MiR-23 regulates the development of adequate heart valves in zebrafish by targeting hyaluronic acid synthase 2 (58). Other miRNAs regulate cardiomyocyte proliferation and apoptosis. MiR-98 and miR-142, for example, inhibit the activity of transforming growth factor beta-1. Furthermore, in the rodent heart, miR-590 and miR-199 can promote cardiomyocyte proliferation. Overall, these findings suggest that miRNAs play a complex function in various cardiogenic stages (57).

IV. THE FUNCTION OF MICRORNAS IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE

In most countries and states, cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of death. Some miRNAs have been linked to certain conditions in recent studies on the function of miRNAs in CVD production (65). Otherwise, cardiac-specific miRNAs can play a role in cardiovascular disease (66). We've compiled a list of some of the most common and clinically applicable miRNAs in cardiovascular disease.

Cardiomyopathies (also known as cardiomyopathies) are a group of diseases that affect

Relevant morphological phenotypes, dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM), hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, restrictive cardiomyopathy, and arrhythmic cardiomyopathy are the five forms of cardiomyopathies. ARVC (arrhythmogenic right ventricular cardiomyopathy) is a form of arrhythmogenic right ventricular cardiomyopathy (1). Mice lacking the Dicer gene have DCM and heart disease phenotypes, according to some in vivo studies. A similar mutation has been identified in humans with heart disease, showing the importance of miRNAs in the pathogenesis of DCM (67). A similar deficiency is seen when the Drosha gene, which is required for the processing and development of miRNAs, is knocked out (68). In mice, miR-195 overexpression induces hypertrophic development of DCM by targeting mitofusin-2 (MFN2) and F-box/WD repeat-containing protein 7 (FBXW7). MiR-133 knockout mice also have septal abnormalities and acute DCM before reaching maturity (70). Furthermore, the Wnt and Hippo signalling pathways are linked with miR-21-5p and miR-135b, which are not only implicated in the cellular pathophysiology of ARVC but also strongly associated with myocardial fibrosis (71). MiR-208 is a myocardial-specific miRNA that has been linked to arrhythmias, cardiac fibrosis, myocardial hypertrophy, MIs, and heart failure (72). MiR-208a is needed for stress-induced pathophysiological cardiac conditions, according to recent research (73). MiR-208 is also linked to cardiac hypertrophy since it inhibits SOX6

(72) and induces MYH6 expression in cardiomyocytes (49). Oliveira et al found a close connection between miR-208 expression in cardiac mast cells and hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, implying that miR-208 plays a role in disease progression (74).

4.2. Congenital heart diseases

Congenital heart defects are anatomical abnormalities in the heart that develop before birth. CHD is thought to be caused by pathological cardiac proliferation or differentiation of cardiomyocytes (75). Atrial septal defects, ventricular septal defect (VSD), and tetralogy of Fallot are the three most common CHD phenotypes (76). MiR-1-1 has previously been shown to play a role in the pathophysiology of VSDs by controlling the expression of BMP receptor type II and gap junction protein alpha 1, both of which undergo specific changes in VSD disease (37). As a result, the deletion of miR-1 causes VSDs (25). VSD causes embryonic lethality in transgenic mice when miR-1-2 is deleted (26). Animal models of miR-1 abnormalities have also shown a variety of CVDs, including VSD, heart arrhythmias, and electrical conduction disruptions (23,26). By cardiac septation, morphogenesis, and valve development, miR-196a deregulation contributes to the formation of atrioventricular septal defects (76). Early cardiac-specific miR-195 overexpression during heart embryogenesis has been linked to VSD in mice (77). Furthermore, miR-17-92 regulates the expression of BMP receptor type II, which is thought to be essential for smooth muscle cell differentiation, proliferation, and fibrous matrix formation (78). In miR-17-92 knockout mice, Ventura et al published VSD pathology (53).

4.3. Cardiovascular disease

Heart failure is a pathological disorder in which the capacity of the ventricles to fill with or discharge blood is impaired due to a simple or functional deficiency. At the cellular level, heart failure is linked to cardiomyocyte hypertrophy, cardiomyocyte apoptosis, and changes in cardiac gene expression (81). MiR-1 and miR-208a are highly expressed in the heart and have been linked to cardiac hypertrophy (79). Furthermore, the overexpression of miR-23a, miR-23b, miR-24, and miR-214 in cardiomyocytes will induce hypertrophic growth (80). Yan et al. claim that myocardial overexpression of miR-195 in transgenic mice is needed for the promotion of heart failure several weeks after birth (57). In rat cardiomyocytes, the overexpression of miR-92, which is downregulated in heart failure, affects the regulation of fetal gene expresses (81).

4.4. Other CVDs

MI, which result in cardiac remodeling and hypertrophic myocardial growth, have been linked to miRNA deregulation. MiR-29 family members stimulate collagen expression by manipulating collagen, fibrillin, and elastin genes, whose expression decreases in the region adjacent to the infarct. As a result, chemically engineered antisense oligonucleotides, dubbed "antimiRs," may be used to downregulate this miRNA, making them a possible therapeutic option for cardiac fibrosis (82). Members of the miR-15 family are upregulated in heart failure and cardiac ischemia, and they also cause apoptosis by targeting the antiapoptotic factor B-cell lymphoma 2. As a result, these miRNA families serve as negative regulators in cardiac repair under stressful conditions (82). Interestingly, members of the miR-15 family are upregulated in cardiac tissue since MIs. Under hypoxic conditions, inhibiting miR-15 improves cardiomyocyte viability in vitro and decreases ischemia-induced heart function dysfunction in mice (57). MiR-15 (83), miR-494 (84), and miR-210, in particular, play a role in cardiac ischemic/reperfusion damage. MiR-320 also plays a role in the control of mediated heart damage and the promotion of cardiomyocyte apoptosis (85). MiR-92a is another endothelial cell-specific miRNA that regulates angiogenesis and the functional regeneration of damaged tissues after MIs (86). By regulating the expression levels of the tumor suppressor Kruppel-like factor 4 and mitogen-activated protein kinase 4 in endothelial cells, miR-92a inhibition facilitates angiogenesis and cardiac activity after cardiac injury and MI (87). In human and mouse models of cardiac hypertrophy, the expression of miR-133 and miR-1 is reduced. As a result, in vitro overexpression of miR-133 or miR-1 causes cardiac hypertrophy to be repressed (40).

V. THE THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF MIRNAS

Despite their limited scale, miRNAs can perform several functions at the same time. As a result, they can be considered suitable for therapeutic purposes, especially in the field of cardiovascular disease (88). In this respect, science tends to be mostly focused on two therapeutic approaches: suppressing endogenous miRNAs linked to a specific disease and replenishing miRNAs that are downregulated under pathological conditions. Injecting adeno-associated viruses with miRNAs, which results in long-lasting expression of the target miRNAs, is one way to upregulate miRNAs for therapeutic purposes. Another method is to use modified synthetic oligonucleotides that can imitate the functions of endogenous microRNAs (89). Inhibition of endogenous miRNAs, on the other hand, involves the use of antimiRs, miRNA sponges, and small inhibitory molecules (90). Antagomirs, also known as antimiRs or blockmirs, will stop the progression of CVDs at any point by controlling miRNA expression (91). The medicinal delivery of locked nucleic acid (LNA) antimiR-15 reduces infarct size and inhibits cardiac remodeling, according to Hullinger et al (83). In animal models of heart failure, inhibiting miR-208a with LNA-modified antimiRs significantly reduces cardiac remodeling while improving cardiac efficiency (92). Under stressful environments, miRNA-34 family members miR-34a, miR-34b, and miR-34c are overexpressed. In mice with preexisting MIs, suppression of the miR-34 family by injecting LNA antimiRs is thought to be advantageous (93). In pre-clinical models, antimiR-15 and antimiR-208 have been used to treat post-MI remodeling and heart failure, respectively (91). The injection of miR-320 antimiRs reduced myocardial fibrosis and apoptosis in a rat model of myocardial ischemia (85). MiR-132 controls hypertrophy and autophagy in cardiomyocytes by specifically targeting the transcription factor forkhead box O3 (FOXO3). Furthermore, blocking miR-132 with antimiRs prevents mice from cardiac hypertrophy and heart failure (94). MGN-1374, which targets miR-15 and miR-195, is a miRNA-based compound in the preclinical stage for the treatment of post-MIs. The miRNA-based drugs MGN-2677,

MGN-4220, MGN-5804, MGN-6114, and MGN-9103, which target miR-143/145, miR-29, miR-378, miR-92, and miR-208, respectively, are also in clinical trials (95). Overall, these findings show that anti-miRs may be a useful tool in the fight against CVDs.

VI. LAST THOUGHTS AND PROSPECTS

CVDs are linked to the worst destruction of human life all over the world. MiRNAs have been established as one of the genetic factors linked to CVDs' genetic origin, frequency, diagnosis, and prognosis, according to research. MiRNAs went unnoticed for a decade after their discovery in 1993; since then, they've been regarded as complex switches because they can not only regulate gene expression but also fine-tune biological processes by deciding the extent of translation repression. Numerous miRNAs have direct or indirect effects on cardiovascular system biology, contributing to the pathogenesis of CVDs. The majority of studies on miRNAs have shown increases and decreases in miRNA levels under different CVD conditions. However, practical classification of these miRNAs that play a role in CVD growth remains elusive. MiRNAs, as well as certain novel molecular networks, have also been implicated in the pathology of CVDs, according to research. The discovery of biomarkers that are effective in the production of a disease will aid in the characterization of the disease and its reaction to pharmacotherapy, highlighting the importance of miRNAs as effective diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers for CVDs. While still in its early stages, the use of miRNAs as therapeutic agents has the ability to dramatically alter therapeutics. To establish miRNAs as effective biomarkers and therapeutic agents, more responsive and precise approaches and technologies are unquestionably needed. Indeed, further analysis with samples from various geographical locations and greater sample volumes is needed to resolve any potential problems or disadvantages. In short, the field of miRNA-based therapeutics is ripe for new discoveries.

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